

**“Gender Norms in 20th century novels: Sozaboy, The Member of the
Wedding, and Dance of Happy Shades as an example”**

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Introduction

Every society has gender roles, and everyone grows up gendered, even if the content and expectation of these roles in different places and times may vary significantly. Gender roles include the duties and manners people learn and adapt from their communities and cultural norms related to the family function, how children experience education, how teachers interpret children's behaviors, and how people present and see themselves in their communities. Any eccentricity/ oddness/ opposition toward the given gender roles is met with scepticism from community members, including families, churches, schools, classrooms, and playgrounds. In other words, parents, grandparents, siblings, teachers, librarians, friends, and even young children are partaking in reinforcing the gender roles within their communities.

The roles of males and females are crucial to their influence on thoughts, speech, behaviors, interests, attitudes, and interactions within their society or culture. Furthermore, what is considered to be "appropriate" for females are different significantly from the one for males. Males and females are expected to exude specific behavioral characteristics to effectively fulfill their "natural" forms of femininity and masculinity. (Canary & Cupach, 1995, p. 233) For example, men are supposed to be stoic, competitive, demanding, and uncompromising to be good fighters and effective providers, while most women's roles are centered on nurturing children, maintaining the home, being warm, inactive, and subordinate to their men. Such behaviors emphasized women's nurturing abilities and men's acceptance of aggression, protection, and provision abilities (Buma, 2012, p. 144). The genders' behavioral expectations signify the traditional masculine and feminine qualities that make males more prone to violence and females more vulnerable members of society. This essay will investigate how gender roles are represented and how males and females are encouraged

and pressured to act accordingly in *The Member of the Wedding* by Carson McCullers, *Sozaboy* by Ken Saro-Wiwa, and *Dance of the Happy Shades* by Alice Munro.

Male gender norms

The path to becoming a man was considered a journey across cultures, and this journey was measured on three fundamental bases: provide, protect, and procreate. These three bases were viewed as columns of the backing of the manhood structure. Consequently, enormous stress is positioned on the remaining columns if one of them is weakened or missing causing the rest to twist and distort (*Cody & Kalbfleisch, 1995, p. 9*)

Providers

Providing at its core is the capacity to domesticate nature, turn disorder into order, and make something worthy of the raw resources of life. It is forceful and firm action that puts together something valuable into the community and family storage. The man's role as a provider is demonstrated in *Dance of happy shades in Boys and Girls* when the protagonist helps her father with work outside. She says that for her father to make a living, he has had to engage in a ferocious job where he raised foxes. He then killed and skinned them when they had prime fur and sold it to companies. She also mentions that her mother hated "*the job being close to the house because it was dirty and smelled*" (Munro, 1968, p. 111).

Work is always considered essential, but not all types of work have the same value. That is what the protagonist tells the reader; for example, she values her father's job on the farm but not her mother's job inside the house. It is evident when the protagonist admires her father's job as she considers it more valuable. She describes, "work done out of doors, and in my father's service, was ritualistically important." (Munro, 1968, p. 117). Contrary to outside work, she neither likes nor values the work inside the house primarily because, as she describes, it is "endless, dreary, and peculiarly depressing" (Munro, 1968, p. 117). However,

even though she thinks highly of her father's job, the job reminds her that it is cruel, bloody, and painful, "my father's bloody apron reminded me. They were fed horsemeat"

(Munro, 1968, p. 118). She elaborates that to raise the foxes, they had to feed them with horses' meat, and usually, the farmers would call her father and Henry (his co-worker) to come and shoot the horses that were not in use anymore because of age or illness.

(Munro, 1968, p. 118). She later finds out that even though her father and Henry had been doing that work for a long time, it still hurt and saddened Henry; when she asks him, "Are you going to shoot him today?" he does not answer her, but instead sings in a "high, trembly, mocking-sorrowful voice" (Munro, 1968, p. 120) it is as if he was hiding his pain and sorrow.

The protagonist realizes the brutality; she releases the horse, Flora, to run away. Her father asks her why she did that, and she cries. He knows she had done it because of her emotions, and he says, "she is only a girl." (Munro, 1968, p. 127). Munro has commented on that, saying, "it is permissible to have fine feelings, impractical sympathies, if you are a girl, because what you say or do does not finally count," (Disney, 2016, p. 195). Although it is allowed to have emotions, and unworkable empathies, if you are a girl, you are not taken seriously in the end. The protagonist realizes the brutality and cruelty the men have to deal with working outside. The incident of letting the horse run away affirms that she could be wrong, and they could be right about her being a girl; working outside with her father in raising foxes is difficult. As a girl, it is difficult to deal with work outside, emotionally and mentally, regardless of physicality; therefore, she does not protest, not even in her heart, and she says, "Maybe it was true." (Munro, 1968, p. 127). Back in the day, men had to do cruel, brutal, and dirty jobs, whereas nowadays, they choose it because these jobs have a high income.

In order to make a living, work is significant for men because it is also the way to establish an identity as providers. Men form their identity through work and measure it by the

money they receive (Schwartz, Patterson, & Steen, 1995). In the past, For boys to become men, they had to work outside to fulfill the providing role, whether the father was alive or dead. In *Sozaboy, the protagonist*, Mene's mom, convinces him to become an apprentice for the only lorry in the village because there will be good job options in the future. Mene says, "If I save my salary and my chop money, I can buy my own lorry and then I will be big man like any lawyer or doctor" (Saro-Wiwa, 1985, p. 11).

In *Sozaboy*, when it comes to supporting society, more responsibility is placed on men's shoulders by paying more taxes than women to the government. Mene tells the reader how men were upset by the fact that women paid less in taxes whether they worked or not "That is no good. Nonsense. Woman can get money from man easy. And woman works hard. Yet when time to collect money reach they will begin to ask man to pay more than woman. Nonsense" (Saro-Wiwa, 1985, p. 8). Historically, traditionally, and even in many cultures now, it is a part of the religion that it is men's duty and obligation to provide for their families and society; moreover, if they do not fulfill that role, they are not considered real men.

Protectors

Protection is essentially the guarding and defending the borders between threat and security, protecting family and society from perpetrators, enemies, and natural disasters. Should that boundary be violated, men will need to act as soldiers, firefighters, and police officers who predominantly are men (Reinisch, Rosenblum, & Sanders, 1987, p. 4). A man demonstrates and develops prowess as the protector, which augments his honor (Blackstone, 2003). An example is the father in *The Member of the Wedding*, who is often absent, working outside to provide for his family. Due to his absence, he does not partake in raising his daughter, who is 12 years old. However, when she runs away from the house, leaving him a farewell letter, he immediately acts and calls law enforcement to prevent her from leaving the

town and stopping her from such a foolish act. She is still young and needs protection and care (McCullers, 1946, pp. 165-173).

Mene also illustrates this in *Sozaboy*. When there were troubles in other places around the country, the people in his village pressured him to join the Soza/army to defend the community. They are projecting on him what they believe: a son of their village should contribute to protecting his country. The old men on the playground, his love/wife, and his environment engage in making him join the army. As a form of social pressure, they called him “Sozaboy” (*Saro-Wiwa, 1985, p. 61*) when he crossed by them. It confuses him because he thinks they are calling someone else, but they assure him it is him they meant to call. One old man, Zaza, always proudly tells how he fought against Hitler in World War II. He says directly, “let Mene them go and fight” (*Saro-Wiwa, 1985, p. 43*). His love, Agnes, agrees to marry him on the condition that he joins Soza/military because she wants a strong, brave man who can fight and defend her (*Saro-Wiwa, 1985, p. 19*).

Even when Mene is in a bar called African Upwind Bar, he hears two men talking about the war and fighting. He hears the tall man answering the short man, saying, “like to fight. Yes. It is good thing to fight. If somebody take your thing by force, if ‘e want by force to do something Wey you no like to do, then you fit fight am” (*Saro-Wiwa, 1985, p. 17*). At the church, he sees Sozas/soldiers passing by, singing songs that praise war and death. As a result, he joins the army, which is nothing like he has been told: it is more like a nightmare. He is traumatized and lost between two identities: the simple, innocent boy and the soldier who has witnessed war but run away. He cannot become a soldier/killing machine, and when he returns, his old life was disappeared because the war has destroyed it. This is also the case for two subjects in Elin’s essay *The Child Soldier Narrative and the Problem of Arrested Historicization* when one mentions that she sometimes feels six years old and sometimes 100 years old. The other subject explains that anyone who goes to war becomes a different person

who only thinks of killing people (Coundouriotis, 2010). As a result of being lost, Mene chooses to run away if anyone mentions war or fighting. As seen, it is clear that men do not always have the choice to fulfill the protection role or not. They are often obligated or pressured to do so, like calling for military service. It is a call for duty and responsibility to defend their country.

Procreators

Procreation is a man's responsibility to achieve; therefore, he has to pursue a woman and successfully impregnate her, thus creating an enormous and sturdy family that expands his genes as much as possible (Hubin, 2013, p. 76). The act of initiating has traditionally been considered a men's role. An example is the soldier in *The Member of the Wedding* who meets Frances, the protagonist, and invites her for a date at the Blue Moon hotel, where he was staying. After they have had a conversation, the soldier takes her to his room, wrongfully thinking that she is old enough; she is only 12 years old. He also thinks she has given him her consent as she did not object, but Frances is naïve and does not know how to object, and despite being uncomfortable, she goes with him. When the soldier caresses and kisses her, she is horrified. However, she finds the courage to bite his tongue and hits him with a glass pitcher (McCullers, 1946, p. 149). Frances was interested in the soldier only as a gateway to connect with the outside world; meanwhile, he was interested in getting her into bed: Her goal was to gain confidence for her brother's wedding, whereas he wanted sex. Because of her self-doubting, she strives to appear and behave like an adult. Frances represents herself as a sexually mature female as she unintentionally leads the soldier to treat her like one; luckily, she prevents him from raping her by hitting him (Groba, 1994, p. 140). In her book *Growing up female: Adolescent girlhood in American fiction*, Barbara A. White notices that the female adolescent in novels rejects the idea of sex and is frightened of it. As Barbara sees it, the

reason is that sex for young female protagonists entails submission to a man's dominance, so it is the loss of sovereignty they fear the most (White, 1985, p. 103).

The second example of men initiating sex is in the *Thanks for the ride* story. While George, the cousin, and the protagonist, Dick, are sitting in Pop's, a girl comes in and sits down on a stool. Even though George pretends he is not attracted to her, saying, "Never Mind" (Munro, 1968, p. 47), he soon after goes to sit next to talk to her. After five minutes, he brings her with him to introduce her to Dick (47). These examples confirm that earlier on men were the initiators, however, the women's reactions varied depending on their situation/socio-economic status, desire, and maturity.

Frances' incident was because of a lack of maturity and miscommunication between her and the soldier in *The member of the wedding*. Adelaide, however, wanted to go out with George in *Thanks for the ride*. Nevertheless, there were and still are situations women are forced to act in a specific way. A good example is Lois in *Thanks for the ride*. When Dick asks whether she liked her boyfriend, she answers, "Oh, sure! I should, shouldn't I? I should get down on my knees and thank him. That's what my mother does. He brings her a cheap old spotted elephant—" (Munro, 1968, p. 54). Even when Dick asks why she wears a dress, she answers him, "I wanted to show you guys" (Munro, 1968, p. 55). Thus, women's response to men depends on many factors, as demonstrated; by their understanding of the social situation, their desires, and economic situation, which has pressured them to behave in a particular way against their will, as in Lois's case.

Providing, protecting, and procreating have been men's fundamental responsibilities in almost every society and culture and are still in some. Societies have given men these roles due to their physicality and strength. Therefore, men were expected live up to the standards that society had structured for them.

Female gender norms

Womanhood has been considered in contrast to manhood in most cultures. This journey has been measured on multiple bases: nurturing, caring, housework, accommodating, passiveness, gentle, politeness, and modesty (Spence & Camille, 1995, p. 107). Womanhood functioned as the core and manhood as the shell of society. However, when a woman stepped out of her expected roles, she would either be distasted, shamed, pressured to step back, or face serious consequences (Groba, 1994, pp. 147-148)

Silence in men's presence

A commonly expected behavior for a woman was to remain silent in the presence of a man, not to interfere in a man's business, and to obey what the man ordered. Silence and submission are the opposite of charge and leadership (1Timothy 2:8-14). The obvious example in *Sozaboy* is when chief Birabee gathers everyone to inform them that the government has ordered him to collect taxes. The men were allowed talk, the women not. "Anything the men talk. Women must do. Dukana people say woman does not get to mouth. And it is true" (Saro-Wiwa, 1985, p. 8). Another example is when the father in the *Boys and Girls* story decides to banish his daughter, the protagonist, from working with him after she lets the horse run away. She remained silent and did not object even if she wanted to. She knows she can no longer work with him when he says, "she's only a girl" (Munro, *Boys, and girls*, 1968, p. 127).

Men have not always imposed gender roles but, sometimes, even women, as it manifests in other places in the *Dance of Happy Shades*. This happens in *Boys and Girls* when the protagonist asks questions, but her grandmother silences and rebukes her, saying, "that's none of girls' business" (Munro, 1968, p. 110). Likewise, in the story *Thanks for the ride* while Lois and Dick were drinking in the car, she would hand him the bottle and say "thank you" in a

well-behaved manner. Later, she confesses that her mother had taught her, “you have to act grateful to those guys, you know, or they say you’re bitching” (Munro, 1968, p. 54). Even though women also imposed social norms upon other women, many will argue that these women have been raised in a male-dominated environment and, consequently, have an internalized patriarchal view (Radu, 2014).

Accepted behaviors

A woman should not display specific behaviors such as sexual language or initiation of sexual activity in many cultures and religions. It is considered immoral, shameless, and promiscuous when done by women (Perz, et al., 2017), whereas considered bold and appreciated behavior when done by men. This may be seen in *Sozaboy* when Mene meets Agnes at the bar: Agnes fascinates Mene with her beauty and erotic body, and he cannot resist the urge to catch a glimpse of her breasts. Then, she moves, allowing him to get a better look. Mene is also surprised by how Agnes speaks to him as she is direct and even sexual, but all Mene thinks is how she is not shy and how a girl can talk like that to him. He repeats on multiple occasions that the girl is not shy, “Abi, the girl no dey shame” (Saro-Wiwa, 1985, p. 14). While dancing, Mene becomes aroused by Agnes, so she goes even further with her sexual language by calling his penis a snake. Even though she is not a shy girl, he likes her, “I tell you, I like a baby who do not shame” (Saro-Wiwa, 1985, p. 18).

The accepted behavior is not limited to sexuality but also covers how to conduct oneself within the social atmosphere. A good example in *the Boys and Girls* story is when the protagonist’s grandmother instructs her how to behave, saying, “Girls don’t slam doors like that.” and “Girls keep their knees together when they sit down.” (Munro, 1968, p. 119). Women have been instructed not only how to behave but also how to be. For instance, in *The Office*, Mr. Malley keeps projecting onto the female protagonist how a woman should be,

saying, “It’d be a different story if you was a man. A woman wants things a bit cosier” (Munro, 1968, p. 65). Certain behaviors have been projected onto women at a very young age from people close to them, such as their mother, grandmother, or the community. Those behaviors have restricted women’s freedom to a large extent historically and nowadays in many societies.

Women and the house

Historically, women have kept their houses in order and were called housewives. Their role was primarily to nurture and care for their families, mainly done in the house. Shopping, cooking, nursing, housekeeping, cleaning, and caring for children was done by the woman who was not given the opportunity to work outside. This is what the protagonist’s mother does in the *Boys and Girls*. The protagonist works with her father, but her mother does not think it is a real help for the father, so she says, “wait till Laird gets a little bigger, then you’ll have a real help” (Munro, 1968, p. 117). This shows that her mother believes that women and girls are supposed to stay inside the house, and men and boys work outside. She underlines this by saying, “I just get my back turned and she runs off. It’s not like I had a girl in the family at all” (Munro, Boys, and girls, 1968, p. 117).

Toward the end of *The Member of the Wedding*, Frances starts doing house chores, such as making sandwiches and doing laundry: “Frances placed the sandwiches on a plate, along with eight chocolates and some salted nuts...at twelve o’clock” (McCullers, 1946, p. 177). This can be seen as a sign of Frances’ acceptance and an attempt to fit into the female category of gender norms after a long struggle throughout the novel. Barbara White and Loise Westling have criticized McCullers’ novel. White described it as “less a novel of initiation into ‘acceptance of human limitation than a novel of initiation into acceptance of female limits” (Earthman, 2003, p. 192). Westling notes that the double edge of identities, half male and half female, is being framed negatively “for the novel’s entire movement is toward Frankie’s

ultimate submission to the inexorable demand that she accepts her sex as female” (Groba, 1994, p. 142). Even when women obtained the possibility to work other than as housewives in the mid of the 20th century, they still carried most of the house tasks on their shoulders.

The house-women relationship is tied that the protagonist in *The Office* story, who is a writer, cannot just make a separation from the house. She cannot bring her work into the house because she can neither ignore the phone ring nor ignore children crying behind her closed door, unlike her husband, who can. The idea of their mother behind a closed door is outraging for children because she is such a big part of the house, “She is the house; there is no separation possible” (Munro, 1968, p. 60). Pregnancy and taking care of infants have contributed basically to assigning the role to women. However, even though women contribute massively to society in most professions nowadays and most tasks and jobs are manageable for everyone, women are still struggling with their relation to the house, which probably has psychological reasons on a deeper level that would be interesting to study.

Conclusion

Women and men have shared life responsibilities and collaborated throughout history to improve their lives. Men have been obligated to provide with their physical strength; examples are bricklayers, where the majority are still men. Men have been trained to be leaders and protectors of their families and societies until today; globally, most soldiers are men, and joining the army is obligatory for men in most countries. The last men’s role this essay discloses is procreation. Men are the initiator of sexual activity as George and the soldier did in the stories; even nowadays, they still are. Women rarely initiate such acts because of society, religion, and traditions. With these three roles, providing, protecting, and procreating, men are predicted to demonstrate certain behaviors, such as aggression, affirmativeness, and impoliteness. At the same time, women have been expected to be nurturing and caring, so with those roles, particular behavior was expected like being polite,

courteous, and empathetic. As a sign of politeness, they are expected to remain silent in men's presence or behave contemptuously, as Lois learned from her mother. Moreso, many behaviors were and still are imposed on women from when they were little girls so that when they grow up, it is the norm for them. The furious thing is that the housewife role has been attached to women to the extent that they are the house, with no difference. Many women know exactly what it feels like, while men can never know. The previous roles have been encouraged, pressured, and in some cases enforced by families and communities for their members to display and to have specific behavior according to their gender roles; otherwise, the men were considered weak, cowardly, unworthy, and less of a man while for women described as rude, shameless, "bitching" or prostitute.

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